

Systemic HER3 ligand-mimicking nanobioparticles enter the brain and reduce intracranial tumour growth.

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SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS

1.1 Recombinant protein production. Recombinant HPK proteins were produced from the pRSET-A bacterial expression vector, which adds an N-terminal hexahistidine sequence for the metal chelate affinity purification of fusion proteins. The plasmid construct encodes the receptor-binding region of neuregulin-1 α (amino acids 35–239, comprising the Ig-like and EGF-like domains)¹ expressed as an amino-[N]-terminal fusion to the penton base sequence followed by a carboxy-[C]-terminal decalysine.² To produce the fusion protein in bacteria, 50 mL cultures of *Escherichia coli* BLR(DE3)pLysS transformed with the indicated pRSET constructs were grown to turbidity at 37°C, with vigorous agitation. Cultures were expanded into 500 mL cultures and induced with 0.4 mM isopropyl β -d-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) once the culture reached an optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) of 0.6–0.8. Incubation continued 3 h after induction, after which the cells were pelleted via centrifugation for 20 minutes at 2,500 G and resuspended in 5 mL lysis buffer (50 mM NaH₂PO₄; 50 mM NaCl; pH 8) containing 0.1% Triton X-100 and 1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (PMSF). After one freeze-thaw cycle, 10 mM MgCl₂ and 0.01 mg/mL DNase I were added, and lysates were gently agitated at RT until viscosity was reduced. Lysates were then transferred to ice, followed by the addition of NaCl and imidazole to 1 M and 10 mM final concentrations, respectively. Lysates were clarified by centrifugation at 4°C, followed by fast protein liquid chromatography (FPLC) affinity purification, programmed with a stepped gradient of imidazole (ranging from 0–500 mM) in 50 mM NaH₂PO₄ and 1 M NaCl. Fractions containing eluted protein (approximately 92 kDa by immunoblot) were buffer exchanged by ultrafiltration in storage buffer (20 mM HEPES, pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 10% glycerol).

1.2 Structural modeling and molecular dynamics (MD) simulation. The HPK monomeric and pentameric structures were generated, as previously described.² A truncated

version of the HPK monomer and pentamer was built (tHPK) to model the effect of pH on the titratable residues in the penton base core of the HPK pentamer. Protein sequence of tHPK monomer was: TGGRNSIRYSELAPLFDTRVYLVDNKS
TDVASLNYQNDHSNFLT TVIQNNDYSPGEASTQTINLDDRSHWGGDLKTILHTNMPNVNEFMF
TNKFKA
RVMVSR LPTKDNQVELKYEWVEFTLPEGNYSETMTIDLMNNAIVEHYLKVGRQNGVLESDIGV
KFDTRNFRLGFDPVTGLVMPGVYTNEAFHPDIILLPGCGVDFTHSRLSNLLGIRKRQPFQEGFRI
TYDDLEGGNIPALLDVDAYQASLKDDTEQGGGGAGGSSNSSGSGAEENSNAAAAAMQPVEDM
NDHAIRGDTFATRAEEKRAEAEAAAEEAAPAAQPEVEKPKKPKVIKPLTEDSKKRSYNLISNDS
TFTQYRSWYLAYNYGDPQTGIRSWTLLCTPDVTCGSEQVYWSLPDMMQDPVTFRSTRQISNF
PVVGAELLPVHKS SFYNDQAVYSQLIRQFTSLTHVFNRFPENQILARPPAPTITTVSENPALTD
HGTLPLRNSIGGVQRVTITDARRRTPYVYKALGIVSPRVLSSRT.

The pentameric core structure of the tHPK particle was investigated under 4 different pH conditions (pH=7, 5, 3, 1). The protonation states of the titratable residues were obtained from the propKa server³⁻⁴ yielding a corresponding net charge on the tHPK bioparticle at different pH values: -60 at pH 7, -5 at pH 5, +255 at pH=3, and +300 at pH=1. The tHPK molecular structures at 4 pH levels (tHPK7, tHPK5, tHPK3, and tHPK1) were relaxed using implicit solvent generalized born molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with the AMBER ff14SB force field⁵ that are part of the AMBER simulation package⁶. The protonation states of the titratable residues were set for the specific pH values and not allowed to change during the biophysical simulations. All bioparticle structures were relaxed using 10 nanoseconds of simulation time. The pH 5 and 7 (tHPK5/tHPK7) bioparticles were simulated for an additional phase of 50 nanoseconds as pH 1 and 3 (tHPK1/tHPK3) pentameric bioparticles broke apart into monomers within the first phase of 10 nanoseconds.

1.3 Particle assembly. Near-infrared (NIR) particles were generated by combining HPK with an Alexa Fluor® 680 end-labeled single-stranded oligonucleotide (ssON) with the sequence 5'-Alexa680-CGCCTGAGCAACGCGGCGGGCATCCGCAAG obtained from Integrated DNA Technologies (IDT). A 4:1 molar ratio of HPK:ssON was incubated at RT for at least 20 min in HEPES-buffered saline (HBS). Particles were filtered twice using 100-kDa molecular weight cutoff (mwco) ultrafiltration devices. Filtrates and retentates were assessed for protein concentration using a Bradford assay, and the ssON payload was assessed by fluorescence at 680 nm using a Spectramax M2 spectrophotometer.

To generate HerDox particles, non-labeled oligonucleotides containing the same

sequence as ssON and its reverse complement were annealed to form oligonucleotide duplexes, as described previously.⁷ HerDox particles were then generated by combining oligonucleotide duplexes (OND) with doxorubicin (Dox) at a molar ratio of 1:10 OND:Dox for 10 min at RT in Tris-buffered saline (TBS; 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.4; 150 mM NaCl), with inversion and agitation. HPK was added at a 4:1 ratio of HPK:OND:Dox. The mixtures were subjected to ultrafiltration using 100-kDa mwco membranes to isolate assembled particles from unassembled components. The OND concentration was quantified by spectrophotometric absorbance at 260 nm after the heparin-mediated release of nucleic acids, as previously described.² The Dox concentration was determined using absorbance at 480 nm, followed by the application of Beer's Law using the extinction coefficient of Dox=8030 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The protein content was measured by spectrophotometric absorbance using the Bradford method (Bio-Rad dye assay). HerOND was generated in similar fashion but with the Dox omitted.

To assemble HerGa particles, S2Ga corrole was slowly titrated into an HPK solution while stirring in a sterile glass vial and a stirring bar, followed by the incubation of the mixture of HPK with S2Ga (30:1 molar ratio; S2Ga:HPK) at RT for at least 1 hour in phosphate-buffered saline (pH 7.4) to produce the HerGa complex. The complex mixture was subject to ultrafiltration using a 50K molecular-weight-cutoff membrane to isolate assembled particles from free unassembled components. The stoichiometry of corrole to HPK was verified by measuring optical absorbance at its maximum wavelength and calculated using the Beer-Lambert law. The protein in the particle was quantified by measuring the spectrophotometric absorbance using the Bradford assay (Bio-Rad dye assay) or measuring the absorbance at 280 nm.

HPK protein and NBP preparations were routinely assayed for presence of endotoxin and processed for subsequent removal if needed so that endotoxin levels in injection formulations equated <2 EU/kg body weight, which is sustained below the FDA recommended maximum permissible endotoxin level of 5 EU/kg body weight for drugs distributed in the United States.⁸ Endotoxin levels were determined using an LAL Chromogenic Endotoxin Quantification Kit following the manufacturer's protocol (Pierce, REF 88282). If needed, endotoxin removal was performed using a Pierce High Capacity Endotoxin Removal Spin Column following the manufacturer's protocol (REF 88274). Recovery of the protein after endotoxin removal was found to be between 90- 95%.

Particle preparations were incubated at 4°C (on ice) for up to 4 days before transfer to longer term storage which entailed aliquoting, flash freezing, and storage of aliquots at -20°C unless otherwise indicated. These preparations were used for downstream biological evaluation (in cellulo and in vivo treatments). When needed, aliquots were thawed on wet ice and then

brought to room temperature before biological testing. Lyophilization as an additional storage option is undergoing active investigation and requires an evaluation of different buffer conditions and excipients appropriate for virus and protein stability⁹ that is beyond the scope of the current study.

1.4 Electron microscopy. Particles were prepared for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) by dispersion in hexane followed by dropping onto an amorphous carbon coated grid. Fixed samples were imaged using a TF20 (FEI Tecnai) transmitting electron microscope fitted with a field emission gun operated at 200 kV. Images were acquired using a TIETZ F415MP CCD camera and processed using TIETZ Tomography package.

1.5 Electrophoretic mobility shift assay (EMSA). HPK was assembled in increasing ratios (1:1, 3:1, 5:1, 8:1, 10:1, and 15:1) with 10 picomoles of 5' AlexaFluor488 oligonucleotide from IDT (5' CGCCTGAGCAACGCGGCGGGCATCCGCAAG 3') in 1X annealing buffer (10 mM Tris pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, and 1 mM EDTA). The resulting samples were split into 2 fractions; one fraction was directly loaded on the agarose gel after adding an equivalent volume of the annealing buffer, and the other fraction was incubated with an equivalent volume of a mixture of proteinase K (from Invitrogen, cat# 25530015) and proteinase K buffer (10 mM Tris HCl pH 8.0, 20 mM CaCl₂, and 50% Glycerol). The samples were digested with proteinase K for 1 hour at 50°C. Then, the samples were loaded on the 0.8% agarose gel and electrophoresis was conducted for 2 hours at 100 volts. The gel was imaged directly on an ImageDoc system. Proteinase K was used at a final concentration of 1 mg/mL in each sample loaded on the gel.

1.6 Serum digest (protection) assay. Free dsOND alone (60 pmol) or preincubated with HPK (2 µg for 30 min at RT) was incubated in whole (100%) active mouse serum at 0° and 37°C for 1 h and then subjected to agarose gel electrophoresis followed by ethidium bromide staining to visualize intact dsOND. Heat Inactivated (H.I.) serum was used as a control.

1.7 Dynamic light scattering (DLS). A Malvern ZEN 3600 Zetasizer Nano was used for DLS analyses. A typical analysis comprised three or more measurements per sample, with each measurement comprising 100 runs and an average of 34K particle counts/sec (kpcs). The reported average is the particle size determination parameter, which yields the most frequent particle size detected in the sample while accounting for intensity fluctuations associated with larger particles. The intensity of the particles was computed via Zetasizer Software version 7.01,

which applies the Stokes–Einstein equation to correlate changes in the scattering intensity and particle movements.

1.8 Cells. The following cell lines were originally obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC): a mouse triple-negative mammary tumor line (4T1), a human breast tumor-derived melanoma line (MDA-MB-435), human triple-negative breast cancer lines (BT-549, MDA-MB-468, MDA-MB-231), human glioma lines (LN229, U251), a mouse fibroblast line (NIH-3T3), and human endothelial cell line (HUVEC). Human brain microvascular endothelial cells (HBMVECs) came from Cell Systems. The 4T1-LucGFP reporter line was generated in house by stable lentiviral transduction of a construct (kindly provided by Dr. M. Kahn, University of Southern California) expressing luciferase and IRES-driven GFP and validated for expression of HER3 on the cell surface. The human HER2+ breast cancer line (JIMT-1) was kindly provided by the lab of Dr. J. Ljubimova, Cedars-Sinai Medical Center. The MDA-MB-231(+) and MDA-MB-231(-) sub-lines were isolated as naturally evolved HER3 positive and HER3 negative TNBC lines (based on cell surface HER3 levels). Dr. Dr. X. Cui, Cedars-Sinai Medical Center, kindly provided the original HER3 negative MDA-MB-231 line and the brain-passaged MDA-MB-435 sub-line (MDA-MB-435-BR4).¹⁰ The human bone-metastatic prostate cancer line (RANKL) was kindly provided by the lab of Dr. L. Chung, Cedars-Sinai Medical Center. The human ovarian cancer line (A2780-ADR) was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. All cell lines were maintained at 37°C with 5% CO₂ under mycoplasma-free conditions in respective complete medium recommended by respective vendors or suppliers supplemented with 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin.

1.9 Patient-derived tissue. De-identified surgical specimens of two independent breast cancer tissues and one normal breast tissue were obtained by informed consent under IRB-approved protocol #29973. Resected breast tissues were immediately placed in cold, sterile DMEM after excision and cut into 2–4 mm pieces before undergoing enzymatic and mechanical dissociation using the gentleMACS™ Octo Dissociator multitissue kit and protocol (Miltenyi Biotec). Resuspended cells were then promptly plated into flasks, multiwell plates, or chamber slides for the indicated treatments. Human brain specimens were received from three fresh male cadaver brains ages 68, 71 and 76. (Tissue for Research, Ltd.) Samples were preserved in 10% buffered formalin.

1.10 Cell surface detection of HER3. To measure relative surface HER3 levels on adherent cells, indicated cells growing on coverslips or in chamber slides were washed with PBS++ (PBS with 1% MgCl₂ and 1% CaCl₂) followed by fixation without permeabilization (to detect cell surface proteins only) and processed for immunocytofluorescence using a HER3 primary antibody (R&D Systems AF4518 1:500) and secondary antibody conjugated with either Alexa Fluor® 647 (Abcam ab150179 1:1000) or with Alexa Fluor® 488 (Abcam ab150177 1:1000, non-GFP tagged cells only). Cell nuclei were counterstained using DAPI followed by mounting as described later in the Immunocytofluorescence section. Whole chambers or coverslips were scanned using a high-throughput digital microscope (Molecular Devices ImageXpress® Pico Automated Cell Imaging System) using a 40× magnification lens. Quantifications are provided as fluorescence intensity (F.I.) per DAPI-positive cell area.

To measure relative cell surface HER3 levels by flow cytometry, adherent cells were detached by incubation in lifting buffer (0.5 M EDTA in Phosphate Buffered Saline, PBS) for 1 h at 37°C, with gentle agitation. Detached cells were collected, washed with PBS++ (PBS with 1% MgCl₂ and 1% CaCl₂), counted using the forward scatter of unstained samples before fixing with 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) for 10 min, followed by rinsing with PBS (3 × 5 min), and suspension in blocking buffer (1% Bovine Serum Albumin, BSA, in PBS) at room temperature (RT) for 1h with gentle agitation. Cells were then divided into aliquots each containing 1 × 10⁶ cells and rinsed with PBS (2 × 5 min). Where indicated samples received either HER3 primary and secondary antibodies as described earlier. Samples were rinsed with PBS (3 × 5 min) and analyzed using a Moxi GO benchtop cell analyzer (Orflo Technologies, Ketchum, ID).

1.11 Receptor binding. To analyze HPK binding to tumor cells, cells were plated at 1 × 10⁴/well in 96-well plates and maintained for 24 h. Cells were incubated on ice to pre-chill cells, and 1.5 µg of HPK diluted in chilled complete medium was added to each well. Ligand blocking was performed by pre-adsorbing HPK with soluble human HER3 peptide (Sino Biological) at 10× molar excess in PBS before addition to cells. Cells were incubated on ice for 1 h to promote binding but not uptake, then thoroughly washed with PBS++ (PBS with 1% MgCl₂ and 1% CaCl₂), fixed with 4% PFA under non-permeabilizing conditions (to detect cell surface proteins), and processed for enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) per manufacturer's instructions (Thermo cat. Number 00-4201-56) followed by crystal violet (CV) staining for normalization according to cell number. CV staining was carried out by removing cell media and washing cells with PBS containing 0.01% Mg⁺⁺ and 0.01% Ca⁺⁺. The PBS was aspirated and each well was stained with 0.1% Crystal Violet at RT for 15 min. The cells were then washed in PBS with

Mg⁺⁺/Ca⁺⁺ 4 times. After the final wash, each well received 0.1mL 95% ethanol to release the CV. The plate was incubated at RT for 10 minutes before the absorbance at 590nm was measured.

1.12 Intracellular trafficking. The intracellular trafficking of HPK was evaluated following our previously established procedures,² with the following modifications: 12-well plates containing 10,000 cells/well plated on coverslips were briefly pre-chilled and exposed to 7 µg HPK per well in Buffer A for 1 h to promote receptor binding but not internalization. Equivalent samples received 100 nM bafilomycin-A1 in Buffer A for 30 min before adding HPK. Plates were then transferred to 37°C to promote synchronized uptake and intracellular trafficking. Cells were fixed at indicated time points after warming, processed for the immuno-identification of HPK using an antibody that recognizes the polyhistidine tag (RGS-His antibody; Qiagen 1:100), and counterstained with DAPI. Images were acquired using a high-throughput digital microscope (Molecular Devices ImageXpress® Pico Automated Cell Imaging System) using a 40× magnification lens. Exposure times for each fluorescence wavelength remained fixed to compare between treatments and timepoints. Where indicated, vesicular-like sequestration of HPK was quantified by subtracting the measured integrated density (Int D) of extravesicular (e) from the vesicular (v) regions normalized by v, or $(\text{Int } D_v - \text{Int } D_e)/\text{Int } D_v$.

Endosome maturation staining antibodies against RAB7 and early endosome antigen 1 (EEA1) were purchased from Abcam (ab50533 and ab206860, respectively). Samples were imaged using a Leica SPE laser-scanning confocal microscope. Acquired images were imported and separated into individual channels. Individual cells in selected channels were delineated, and pixel overlap was evaluated using ImageJ.

1.13 Subcellular fractionation. Subconfluent (70% confluency) HER3+ MDA-MB-435 tumor cells grown in complete media were rinsed with 1× PBS, serum-starved in Buffer A [Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium (DMEM) containing 20 mM HEPES, pH 7.4; 2 mM MgCl₂; and 3% bovine serum albumin (BSA)] for 1 hour at 37°C, rinsed with 1× PBS, detached with 2 mM EDTA/PBS, and neutralized with double the volume of 1× PBS⁺⁺. An aliquot containing 6 × 10⁶ cells was washed with PBS and resuspended in 0.7 mL Buffer A containing 5 nM indicated proteins (quantified by Bradford Assay). Cells were incubated with rocking for 1 hour at 4°C to promote receptor binding but not uptake, followed by transfer to 37°C to promote synchronized cell uptake. At the indicated time points, cells were pelleted (10 min, 5000 rpm, 4°C) and washed in a mildly acidic buffer (1 mL of 1× PBS, pH 6) for 5 minutes to remove the remaining

cell surface protein. Cell pellets were then rinsed with 1× PBS and processed for subcellular fractionation (Qproteome Cell Compartment Kit, Qiagen; following the manufacturer's protocol). Indicated fractions were isolated, and protein precipitation was performed by incubation in 4 volumes of ice-cold acetone for 15 minutes, followed by pelleting (10 min, 14,000 rpm, 4°C), the removal of the supernatant, and resuspension in storage buffer (10% glycerol and 5% SDS in dH₂O). Samples were subject to reducing sodium dodecyl sulfate-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and immunoblotted using antibodies recognizing recombinant protein (anti-NRG1; NRG1abcam ab180808, 1:5000 dilution in 5% milk) and corresponding fraction controls: cytosolic (GAPDH; R&D Systems, MAB5718, 1:10000 in 3% BSA); cytoskeletal (β -actin; R&D Systems, MAB8929, 2:10000 in 3% BSA); and membrane (TIM23; BD Biosciences, 611222, 6:10000 in 3% BSA). Primary incubation was performed overnight at 4°C followed by incubation with anti-rabbit or anti-mouse HRP-containing secondary at room temperature for 2 hours (Abcam, goat anti rabbit AB6721 and goat anti mouse AB6789 respectively). Immunoblots were imaged using the high sensitivity setting on a Bio-Rad chemidoc imager.

1.14 BBB chip. The organ-on-a-chip is composed of a flexible polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) elastomer that contains two closely apposed and parallel micro-channels (1 × 1 mm top channel and 1 × 0.2 mm bottom channel)¹¹ separated by a porous, flexible PDMS membrane (50- μ m-thick, with 7- μ m-diameter pores, spaced 40 μ m apart, resulting in 2% porosity over a surface area of 0.171 cm² separating the two channels) coated with matrigel in the top channel, and collagen-fibronectin ECM in the bottom channel. Cell aggregates ("EZ-spheres")¹² were derived from human cells obtained through IRB #21505. To generate BBB chips, EZ-spheres containing induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived neural progenitor cells (NPCs) were dissociated into single cells using accutase and were seeded into the top channel ("brain channel") at a density of 1.25×10^6 cells/mL in terminal differentiation media [TDM, containing Rock inhibitor 1:2000 (Stemgent)]. NPCs were allowed to settle for 2 h and were then flushed with TDM without Rock inhibitor. Media was replaced with 100 μ L TDM every other day. Five days later, human induced pluripotent stem cell-derived brain microvascular endothelial like cells (iBMECs) were seeded into the bottom channel ("vascular channel") at 15×10^6 cells/mL in S3 BMEC medium containing Rock inhibitor (1:2000) and inverted for 2 h. A second seeding was performed after 2 h using the same protocol without inversion for 2 h. Following the second incubation period, the BBB chips were flushed with S3 BMEC medium without Rock inhibitor. The following day, chips were flushed with fresh TDM and S4 BMEC medium. The following

day, the chips were added to Emulate, Inc. pods and placed on an active flow of 30 μ L/h. Chips were validated via paracellular permeability assays using dextran-FITC overnight to confirm the barrier function of the chips under flow before release to investigators for experimental testing. Validated BBB chips were treated with NBPs at a concentration equating to 1 μ g/mL of HPK that was passed through the endothelial channel with or without 10:1 blocking peptide purchased commercially from Sinobiological (10201-H08H). After 4 hours of constant flow, the chips were fixed using 4% PFA and subjected to immunocytofluorescent staining.

1.15 Sandwich ELISA. Non-tissue culture-treated polystyrene plates were pre-coated using rabbit anti-Ad5 (Abcam- ab6982) diluted in sodium bicarbonate pH 9.2. Plates were then blocked using 3% BSA. After washing three times with PBS, BBB effluents were incubated overnight. Signal was detected using mouse anti-His antibody from Qiagen (Cat No./ID: 34660 1:500). Anti-mouse horseradish peroxidase (HRP) was used for colorimetric development (Cat No./ID- A8924 1:1000). A650 reads were started 15 minutes after the addition of TMB. Once developed and read using Molecular Devices SpectraMAX M2, the reaction was stopped by adding 1 N HCl, and the A450 was acquired. An HPK standard curve was processed in parallel to quantify HPK NBPs collected from BBB chip effluents.

1.16 Animal subjects. Immunodeficient (NU/NU) and immunocompetent (BALB/c) mice were obtained from Charles River Laboratories, Inc. All procedures involving mice were performed following IACUC-approved protocols #6037 and #5790, in accordance with the institutional and national Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. The criteria for euthanasia included tumor ulceration, interference with ambulation and access to food and water, or body condition score (BCS) of less than 2 (emaciation, prominent skeletal structure, little/no flesh cover, visible and distinctly segmented vertebrae).¹³⁻¹⁴ Blood collected at sacrifice was processed using serum separator tubes (BD microtainer tube with serum separator additive/gel, Becton Dickinson) following the manufacturer's protocol and isolated sera were transferred to an external reference lab (IDEXX BioAnalytics, West Sacramento, CA, USA) that provided the measurements of serum analytes. Samples were provided in a blinded / anonymous fashion (sample labeling lacked identifying information).

1.17 Tumor models. Peripheral breast tumor models used for the biodistribution and therapeutic efficacy studies were established in 6-week-old female mice. For xenograft models, immunodeficient (NU/NU) mice received bilateral flank implants of JIMT-1 human HER2+ breast

tumor cells (1×10^7 cells/implant). For immune-competent models bearing peripheral TNBC tumors, BALB/c mice received bilateral mammary fat pad injections of 4T1-LucGFP cells (1×10^4 cells/injection in 0.1 mL PBS). Bioluminescences of 4T1-LucGFP tumors were acquired as described later below. Primary tumor volumes (height \times width \times depth) were monitored approximately 3 times/week under single-blinded conditions (treatment groups unknown to the individual acquiring measurements). For evaluating therapeutic efficacy, mice were randomized at tumor establishment (≥ 100 – 150 mm³) into separate treatment groups (n=5 mice per group) and received indicated therapeutic reagents or controls by tail vein injection twice per week for 4 weeks. HerDox and lipodox dosages equated 0.2 mg/kg based on doxorubicin content. Additional cohorts shown in the **Supplementary Materials** received 0.02 mg/kg HerDox. Empty particles (lacking the doxorubicin) equated the 0.2 mg/kg dose. Saline (mock) treatments were administered at equivalent volumes as the experimental reagents. HerGa and S2Ga dosages equated 0.2 mg/kg based on gallium corrole content. Because the HPK protein mediates the receptor-targeted delivery of NBPs and targeting to tumors is largely dependent on and limited by HER3 cell surface levels, in vivo dosage concentration, dosing number, and frequency were determined based on the following parameters: circulating blood concentration of drug was based on the minimally effective concentration (MEC) for reducing HER3+ tumor cells (4T1 mouse TNBC) but not HER3- non-tumor cells (NIH-3T3 mouse fibroblasts). From the MEC, we could then determine the therapeutically effective ratio of drug molecules to cell number (drug to cell ratio) and extrapolate this to the estimated cell number in the tumors in vivo, using primary tumor size as an initial gauge.¹⁵ For tumors measured based on bioluminescence, cell numbers were estimated from a calibration curve plotted from the bioluminescence measurements of known tumor cell titrations implanted in control mice. The total desired accumulation of drug in the tumor (drug to cell ratio) informed the total number of dosages to administer at the determined circulating blood concentration of drug. Frequency of dosing is based on the time course of biodistribution and tissue clearance in tumor models. These same parameters were used to design the treatment regimen in mice with IC tumors as described below.

For the implantation of IC tumors, anesthetized 4-week-old female mice were positioned in a stereotactic frame, and a burr hole was created in the skull using a steel bit at 2 mm right of the sagittal and 2 mm anterior to the lambdoid suture. A stereotactic frame was used to guide a Hamilton syringe, and 10,000 cells in 2 μ L were implanted at 4 mm depth. After implantation, bone wax was used to seal the hole, and the incision was sealed with surgical staples, which were removed 5 days later. Immunodeficient NU/NU mice were used for evaluating HerDox and Lipodox (n=12 for HerDox and Lipodox; n=14 for Mock). Treatments were delivered via tail vein

at a dose of 0.004 mg/kg based on doxorubicin content at a regimen meeting the parameters described earlier. Immunocompetent BALB/c mice were used for evaluating HerGa and S2Ga (n=5 per treatment group) each delivered at 0.2 mg/kg based on gallium corrole content at a regimen meeting the parameters described earlier. Tumor growth was monitored via luciferase beginning on day 4 after implantation and randomized before treatments.

To ensure rigor, all measurements were collected in blinded fashion with cohort identities unknown to the researcher.

1.18 Bioluminescence and near-infrared fluorescence acquisition. Luciferase monitoring was performed every four days, beginning on day 4 post-implantation. Mice received 200 μ L intraperitoneal of 30 mg/mL D-Luciferin (Caliper) dissolved in PBS 10 minutes before imaging using an in vivo imaging system (IVIS). D-Luciferin was allowed to circulate in the animals for 15 minutes, followed by imaging using a PerkinElmer IVIS Lumina Spectrum. Total Flux (photons/sec) signals were quantified using equally sized regions of interest (ROI) centered around the cranial region in LivingImage™ software.

NIR image acquisition was performed on freshly excised organs at indicated time points. Average radiant efficiencies ($[p/s/cm^2/sr] / [\mu W/cm^2]$) were quantified using regions of interest (ROI) outlining individual organs in LivingImage™ software.

1.19 MRI. A 9.4 T MRI (BioSpec 94/20USR, Bruker GmbH) was used for imaging tumor locations and volumes. The tumor perimeters were visually aided by intravenous injections of 7.5 μ mol gadovist contrast agent. Mice were imaged under inhaled 1.7% isoflurane anesthetic. Images were collected with an in-plane resolution of 70 μ m using an acquisition matrix of 256 \times 196 and zero filling in the phase encoding direction to 256, using a field of view (FOV) of 1.80 cm \times 1.80 cm. Twenty consecutive 0.7-mm slices covered the tumor implanted region. Two averages were collected, with a repetition time of 750 ms and an echo time of 8.77 ms, for a total scan time of 4.9 minutes using a mouse 4-channel brain array coil (T11071V3, Bruker GmbH) for reception and a whole-body transmission coil (T10325V3, Bruker GmbH) for excitation. Volume calculations for positive contrast brain regions were determined by integration over the entire tumor by a blinded analyzer. For each slice containing tumor-enhanced regions, an ROI was drawn to encompass the area. The area of each slice was multiplied by the slice thickness, and the individual volumes were summed to determine the area of the tumor. The analysis utilized the Bruker Paravision 5.1 software. MRI core staff performed quantifications in a blinded fashion.

1.20 Biodistribution. For the quantification of particle delivery by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), each mouse was administered a single tail vein injection of HPK bioparticles loaded with gallium(III) metallated corrole (HPK-S2Ga or HerGa)⁷ or S2Ga alone, at 1.5 nmoles S2Ga per injection. At 6h after injection (n=2 per treatment), mice were euthanized, and the major organs (brain, heart, kidneys, liver, lungs, spleen, and tumors) were excised, weighed, and transferred to the University of California Los Angeles ICP-MS core facility. Samples were digested overnight and processed by ICP-MS to measure the tissue content of Ga(III) metal.

Each mouse receiving NBPs (n=5) was administered a single tail vein injection of HPK bioparticles loaded with NIR Alexa Fluor 680-labeled oligonucleotides at a dose equal to 1.50 nmoles oligonucleotide/injection. Mice were monitored by epifluorescence imaging at the indicated time points after injection using an IVIS® Spectrum (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA), followed by tissue harvesting and the acquisition of average radiant efficiency ($[p/s/cm^2/sr] / [\mu W/cm^2]$) per tissue. Where indicated, the relative tissue content of NIR-OND was determined based on the extrapolation of measurements acquired from extracted tissue against a standard curve of known NIR-OND titrations in tissue lysates. Tumors were implanted 8 days before mice received systemic NBPs, allowing sufficient time for damaged vessels to repair, and NIR-OND alone was used to detect the possibility of vascular leakage.

Mice (n=5 each treatment) receiving directly labeled protein or particles (NIR-labeled HPK capsomeres, Tz, or BSA) were injected with the indicated treatment through a single tail vein injection at 12 nmol of labeled protein/injection. Proteins were labeled with Alexa Fluor-680 at primary amines and isolated from the unconjugated dye by size exclusion chromatography using a commercial protein labeling kit, following the manufacturer's protocol (LifeTechnologies).

1.21 Immunogenicity assay. Female BALB/c mice (~6 weeks; Charles River) received tail vein injections of empty (no drug) NBPs at 0.5 mg/kg HPK per injection (equating ~0.2 mg/kg HerDox) twice/week for 4 weeks. Serum isolated from blood collected at indicated time points underwent serial dilutions to 1×10^{-4} dilution and processed by ELISA using either empty NBPs (5 μ g/ml, 0.5 μ g/well) or Ad5 (5×10^6 PFU/well) as capture antigens. Mouse Ig was detected using horseradish peroxidase-conjugated antimouse antibody, and ELISAs were performed according to standard procedures. Serial dilutions of mouse Ig were used as reference antibody titers.

1.22 Immunocytofluorescence and immunohistofluorescence. For immunocytofluorescent staining, adherent cells grown on coverslips or in chamber slides were washed 3–4 times with 1% MgCl₂ in PBS, then fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 15 min at room temperature, followed by washing three times with PBS, then incubation in 50 mM ammonium chloride in PBS for 5 min at room temperature to quench autofluorescence. Cells were washed again three times in PBS, then incubated in 0.1% Triton X-100 in PBS for 5 min at room temperature followed by immunostaining protocol described below.

For paraffin-embedded tissue specimens, slides prepared from sectioned specimens were deparaffinized by incubation in a dry oven for 1 h, washed with xylene 5 × 4 min each, and sequentially rinsed in 100%, 95%, 90%, 80%, and 70% ethanol, 2 × 3 min each. The slides were then submerged in water. Epitope retrieval was performed by incubating the slides for 30 min at 37°C in 10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, 0.05% Tween 20, pH 9.0. Peroxidase inactivation was performed using 3.0% H₂O₂ for 30 minutes followed by incubation in True Black lipofuscin autofluorescence quencher (Goldbio cat # TBH-250-1).

Slides were blocked in 1% BSA for 2 hours, then incubated in primary antibodies at 4°C overnight followed by washing and staining with species appropriate fluorescent secondary antibodies for 2 hours at room temperature in the dark. Slides were counterstained with indicated reagents delineating nuclei and cytoskeleton, then mounted with 4'6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI)-containing Prolong Antifade (Thermofisher). Primary antibodies against the following targets were used: Claudin-5 (Invitrogen 35-2500 1:50), Ad5 (Abcam ab6982 1:100), HIS-tag (Qiagen 34610 1:100), CAV1 (caveolae marker, ab2910), and HER3 (Thermo Fisher Scientific mouse H3.105.5 [Ab105] 1:500 for patient-derived breast tumor specimens, isolated human endothelial cells, and intracellular trafficking studies in human tumor cells; Cell Signaling rabbit anti-mouse and human HER3 D22C5 for both mouse and human non-tumor brain specimens, and human tumor cell lines; R&D Systems sheep anti-mouse HER3 AF4518 1:400 for BBB chip studies and tissue specimens undergoing co-immunostaining for CAV1). Information on secondary antibodies and HER3 specificity is provided in the **Supplementary Materials**.

1.23 TUNEL Assay. Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick-end labeling (TUNEL) assays was performed, according to the manufacturer's instructions (Roche). Following treatment, slides were counterstained and mounted with 4'6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI)-containing Prolong Antifade (Thermofisher). Images of stained tissues were captured

using a Leica SPE laser-scanning confocal microscope and Molecular Devices ImageXpress Pico, where indicated. Images were analyzed using three independent fields quantifying positive cell signals above threshold determined by unstained controls with equal exposure.

1.24 Statistical methods. Except where indicated, in vitro data are presented as the mean of triplicate samples \pm standard deviation from at least three independent experiments. For normally distributed in vitro data, significant differences were determined by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc analysis, unless otherwise indicated. In vivo data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Non-parametric analyses were used to determine significant differences within in vivo experiments, where appropriate, using Kruskal–Wallis tests followed by Mann–Whitney post hoc analysis. All measurements were taken from distinct samples.

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